

International Journal of Emerging Trends in Education

www.ijete.org.pk

Research Article

School Climate and Academic Achievement: An Investigation of Secondary School Students

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Article Info.	Abstract
Received: 10-Nov-23 Revised: 15-Dec-23 Accepted: 23-Dec-23 Published: 31-Dec-23	<p>This study was conducted to find out the role of school climate in promoting academic achievement of students. The study was descriptive in nature and survey method was used. The population of the study were consisted of two hundred and sixty (260) female and male teachers from government secondary schools of tehsil Kotli. The researcher used simple random sampling technique for the selection of sample. The researcher selected one hundred and fifty four (154) female and male teachers as a sample of the study. The researcher developed a five-point Likert-scale questionnaire as the research instrument of the study. Data were collected by personal visits. The collected data was analyzed through SPSS by using mean score, frequency and percentage. It was found that school provide safe environment for students at school and students treat each other's with respect and the school environment is free from intimidation. It is recommended that educators build up respectful behavior among students through structured curriculum, teacher modeling, and partner intervention, and actively create a positive school climate to ensure conducive learning environment for academic achievement.</p>
Keywords:	School Climate, Academic Achievement, Secondary Level
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How to Cite:	Abbas, A. (2023). School Climate and Academic Achievement: An Investigation of Secondary School Students. <i>International Journal of Emerging Trends in Education</i> , 1(3), 54-69.

Introduction

A school is an educational institution that aims to provide an environment for students to learn under the guidance of teachers (Lamsal 2022). Most countries have a formal education system, which is sometimes necessary. In these systems, pupils progress through a series of schools.

School climate represents the value and characteristics of school life. School climate is based on patterns of school life experiences of students, parents, and school staff and reproduces norms, goals, values, interpersonal relationships, teaching practices, and administrative structures (Luciano, 2023).

School climate is very important for quality education. Over the past fifty years, much research has been conducted on the relationship between school climate and academic achievement (Asvio, 2022). Most research shows that a high-quality school environment is closely related to student success. The performance of students and the behavior of all participants of the school are affected by school climate. Sustainable and positive school climates encourage the development and learning of young people, which is necessary for productive, enriching and nourishing lives in a independent society. This climate includes standards, beliefs, and opportunities that ensure people feel safe publicly, emotionally, and tangibly (Savolainen, 2023).

People are loyal to dear Students, parents and teachers work together to mature, live and pay to a shared school vision (UNESCO 2022). Educators build and encourage attitudes that emphasize the welfares and well-being of learning. Everyone adds to the school's responsibilities and love for the physical setting. Depending on the rules set by teachers and administrators, the school learning environment or the common atmosphere within the environment is one in which students can have different experiences (Chawla & Nature ,2020).

School climate is closely related to the excellence and character of school life. It is based on the concept of school life practices and reproduces norms, goals, values, social relations, teaching, learning and management practices and organizational structures (National School Climate Council). It shows the role of consent in new practices, dramatic change, social and passionate learning, frequency of mental health problems, dominance of passion in schools, victimization, academic achievement and teacher attrition (Weare, 2015).

More, Hoy & Tarter (1992) provides seven foundations for school climate and school wellness while focusing on student success. These policies include: Institutional Honesty, Introduction Structure, Academic Focus, Self-Esteem, Consideration, Resource Support, and Principal Encouragement. Bryk and Driscall (1988) three basic principles of school climate are explained: Formal administrative characteristics, for example, the tasks and relationships between organizational personnel and external gatherings. The shared value system is based on the cultural norms and values of the school environment.

As research begins to establish the relationship between student academic performance and school climate, the alarm bells for research on school climate are getting louder. These judgments use average socioeconomic status and competition work to look at primary schools with varying outcomes and schools with typical outcomes. Researchers have found that certain phases of the school environment can have a significant impact on academic performance in schools. After net

of psychosocial climate variables, socioeconomic position and the cultural composition of the school explained a minor portion of the adjustment (Alam, 2022).

Academic achievement defines academic outcomes and specifies the level at which students achieve learning objectives. Academic success may mean completing a degree of study such as a bachelor's degree. Academic success is usually measured through examinations or constant assessment (Yağcı, 2022).

Achievement can be measured by students' grade point averages, and for organizations, success can be measured by qualification charges (Wu & Zhang 2023). Academic achievement refers to the goal improvement of acquiring educational skills, resources, and knowledge, often across multiple disciplines. It refers to achievement in an academic setting rather than the gaining of general knowledge in a non-academic setting. Academic success revolves around the central goal of perfecting students' educational knowledge. Because of this focus, outcome measurement is often criticized for focusing on comfortable knowledge rather than problem-solving or produce design skills (Yuliatin, 2023). In terms of school climate, it reproduces the social, emotional and moral skills of students, school staff and parents as well as the academic experience of school life. Over the years, research from a variety of historically somewhat anxious surveys has identified research-based school improvement guidelines that are certain to create a safe, caring, accessible, and engaging school (Zysberg & Schwabsky, 2021).

Academic achievement is the degree to which a student learns academic content within a specific period of time. This can be any way for students to achieve short- or long-term academic goals in an academic setting. Academic success must be defined, which is why different goals are used as defining characteristics. Assessing the academic achievement of students is time-limited. In his study, Macneil (2009) found that a good learning environment had an impact on students' achievement of high scores on standardized tests.

Additionally, Pashiardi (2008) discovered that a supportive, amiable, enjoyable, and compassionate educational environment promotes student happiness and optimal learning. According to Naseer and Saeed's (2007) research, there is a significant correlation between student achievement and school size in Pakistan. The results of the same study also show a significant correlation between student achievement and class size. Additionally, there is a positive correlation between student achievement and the school climate.

Review of Related Literature

School Climate

The administrative culture of the school determines the atmosphere of the school (Purwanto, Fahmi, & Sulaiman, 2023). According to Molinari, and Grazia, (2023), defining perceptions of school climate is not easy. School climate refers to all characteristics experienced by students, teachers, and the school organization. Likewise, a decent school not only improves learning and teaching, but also outcomes. All school members, teachers and organizations use all school resources to promote student progress (Grant, 2022).

The climate in schools is included of many factors and has been of unending concern to scholars and researchers. Callebert (2023) Showing that climate is not real; it's a "matter of thought."

Positive factors in school climate include a conducive and encouraging project atmosphere, competent collegiality, and strong relationships with parents in the community. It also creates cohesion and enhances school pride. Whether the climate is positive or negative, hot or cold, all the senses of the human body can tell (Mekashaw, 2022).

Various members contribute to a positive school climate. These members relate to the physical, social and learning environments and organize the school environment. These members improve student educational outcomes and increase student motivation and learning. These members played their part in this. Because of their difficulties, school climate becomes important and good (Zysberg, & Schwabsky, 2021).

A positive school climate means students, teachers, parents, and all members of the community develop satisfying and lasting relationships in teaching and learning (Mboweni, & Taole, 2022).

Many studies show that school climate has a strong effect on student achievement. Likewise, schools and their climate are made up of many factors. These factors also contribute to a school's good performance (Longobard, Pagliuca, & Regoli, 2022). Community climate consists of different elements i.e. physical, social and learning setting and all these elements grow motivation between students. The negative effect of school climate is evident in its level of strength and its response to violence. Inappropriate and dangerous behavior, such as student carrying of weapons, continues in our schools in part due to denial, minimization, justification, blame, hindrance, and lack of support (Assefa, Tilwani, & Moges, 2023).

Dimensions of School Climate

School climate denotes to the overall atmosphere, environment and social relations within the school. It includes many dimensions that work together to promote the overall experience and well-being of students, staff and faculty. Although different frameworks may classify slightly different dimensions, here are some common dimensions of school climate (Konishi, Wong, Persram, Vargas-Madriz & Liu, 2022).

Safety

It refers to the physical and emotional safety of individuals within the school community. It includes measures to stop bullying, violence and harassment, as well as safety measures and practices (Jessiman, Kidger, Spencer, Geijer-Simpson, Kaluzeviciute-Burn & Limmer, 2022).

Relationship

The relational dimension highlights the quality of relationships between students, teachers, staff, and parents. This includes positive relationships, trust, respect and cooperation between different members of the school community (Martin, Horgan, O'Riordan & Maier 2023).

Inclusion and Diversity

It focuses on the extent to which schools value and support diversity, equity and inclusion. This includes creating a friendly and welcoming environment for individuals of all backgrounds, cultures, abilities and identities (Grapin & Pereiras, 2019).

Academic Support

Academic support refers to the extent of assistance and resources provided to students for their learning and academic success. This includes factors such as teacher support, teaching quality, availability of tutoring or guidance, and access to educational resources (Fong, Gonzales, Hill-Troglin Cox & Shinn, 2023).

Physical Environment

The dimensions of school climate cover the physical condition of the school, including purity, maintenance, aesthetics, and comfort. This also includes providing suitable facilities and materials to support learning and extra-curricular activities (Iordye, & Jato, 2023).

Emotional Well-being

It emphasizes the social and emotional comfort for pupils and staff. This involves promoting mental health, self-esteem and emotional support structures within schools, as well as addressing issues related to stress, anxiety and general mental health (Tripon, Gonça, & Bulgac, 2023).

Engagement and Participation

Engagement relates to student, faculty, and staff participation in school activities, decision-making practices, and extracurricular opportunities. This includes opportunities for student management, active participation in class discussions, and participation in clubs, sports, or community service (Sulistiyorini, Junaris, Syafi'i & Mu'awanah, 2022).

Parent and Community Involvement

This dimension reflects the near of engagement and teamwork between the school and parents or careers and the wider community. This includes practical lines of communication, parent-teacher relationships, community partnerships and participation in school events or initiatives (Mayger, & Provinzano, 2022).

Academic Achievement

Academic achievement is characterized in various ways, including proficiency in academic work or the information a student formally acquires in a school subject, sometimes expressed as a percentage of grade. It is defined as academic achievement, involvement in meaningful learning activities, fulfillment, achievement of required knowledge, skills, and abilities, persistence, achievement of academic achievement, and performance after college (Cachia, Lynam, & Stock, 2018). In order to achieve the goals of academic excellence and maximize academic achievement, it would be meaningful to study the correlates of academic achievement and its impact on educators and policy makers.

Childhood academic success can be described as the continuous improvement of an individual's academic abilities over the years (Abdullah, Poetri, Saputra, & Al Haddar, 2023). A child must always aim for academic excellence in order to succeed academically. If a child's upbringing is filled with a range of activities and functions, there are various ways in which they can succeed

academically. Academic performance, often called academic achievement, refers to the degree to which a student, teacher, or institution achieves short- or long-term learning goals. Academic success is demonstrated by achieving educational milestones, such as a bachelor's degree and a high school diploma (Castro-Castillo, Macias, de Rodríguez, & Moreira-Choez, 2023).

Promoting Academic Achievement in students

Promoting student academic success involves using a variety of strategies and interventions to support their learning and development (Osher, Sprague, Weissberg, Axelrod, Keenan, Kendziora, & Zins, 2008). Here are some common types of promoting academic achievement:

Effective Teaching Practices

Use research-based teaching strategies such as clear learning goals, active student engagement and formative assessment, differentiated instruction, and timely feedback to students (Prince, Felder & Brent, 2020).

Individualized Instruction

According to Tzenios (2020), recognize that students have different learning styles and abilities and adapt teaching to meet their individual needs. This may involve a personalized study plan, differentiated assignments or one-to-one tutoring.

Supportive Learning Environment

This deals with creating a positive and inclusive classroom climate that fosters students' sense of belonging and motivation (Glass, Kociolek, Wongtrirat, Lynch, & Cong, 2015). This may include building strong teacher-student relationships, promoting respect and empathy, and creating a safe and supportive learning climate.

Goal Setting and Monitoring

According to Burik (2021), Help students set exact, measurable, reachable, related and time-bound (SMART) goals and display their progress frequently. This enables learners to track their achievements and take control of their own learning.

Study Skills and Time Management

Teach students effective study strategies, organizational techniques, and time management skills. This includes helping them develop habits such as setting goals, prioritizing, creating a study schedule, and using effective note-taking methods (Adams & Blair, 2019).

Parental and Family Involvement

Jeynes (2018) recommended that parents be encouraged to participate in their students' education. This may include regular communication between teachers and parents. This deals with providing parents with resources how to support their children's learning at home, and involving parents in school activities.

Peer Support and Collaboration

Encourage peer interaction and collaboration among students. Group work, cooperative learning activities, and peer tutoring improve comprehension, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills (Ghavifekr, 2020).

Enrichment Programs and Extracurricular Activities

Provide students with opportunities to explore interests, talents, and passions outside of the regular curriculum. This may include participation in clubs, sports, arts, science fairs, and other enrichment programs that promote intellectual development and creativity (Renzulli, 2021).

Technology Integration

Use technology to improve instruction, make knowledge easier to acquire, and provide students opportunity for interactive, interesting learning (Upor, 2023).

Mentoring and Guidance

This involves providing students with tutoring and guidance from faculty, advisors, or upperclassmen. Mentoring relationships can provide academic and emotional support, goal setting, and career guidance (Abdallah, Altarawneh & Awwad Alomoush, 2022).

Research Objectives

1. To identify the various dimensions of school climate that influences the student's performance.
2. To examine the role of school climate in promoting academic achievement of students.

Research Methodology

The major aim of this study was to find out the role of school climate in promoting academic achievement of secondary school students. The study was quantitative in approach, descriptive in nature. Furthermore, survey method was used to collect the data from the respondents. All the teachers of secondary level in Kotli AJ&K were the population of the study. Simple random sampling technique was used for the selection of sample. As the purpose of the study was to measure the role of school climate in promoting academic achievement of students, so the researcher developed a questionnaire based on the dimensions of school climate in promoting academic achievement of students. The questionnaire was consisted of total four dimensions; first dimension consisted of six statements while other three dimensions consisted of eight statements. Hence, the questionnaire was consisted of 30 statements. Five-point Likert scale was used to collect the responses from the respondents. Validity of instrument was checked from two experts of the field of education. For the purpose of pilot testing, the questionnaire was distributed among 30 secondary school teachers who were not the part of final survey. The purpose of pilot testing was to check the readability usability and reliability of the instrument. Reliability of instrument was checked by Cronbach's alpha statistical technique. The reliability of the instrument was 0.85 which was acceptable for using instrument for final survey. The researcher personally visited the

sampled schools and collected the data. For the purpose of analysis, the researcher applied frequency, percentage and mean through Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Results

Table 1

Mean analysis of safety

Sr. No	Statements	N	Mean
1.	I provide safe environment for students at school	154	4.53
2.	My students treat each other with respect	154	3.93
3.	The school environment is free from intimidation	154	4.21
4.	The school encourages a cultural safety	154	4.27
5.	My students feel safe during school events	154	4.35
6.	The school responds quickly to safety concern	154	4.28
7.	Students and staff work together to maintain safety	154	4.39
8.	My students feel comfortable asking questions in class	154	4.15

Table 1 shows the mean scores of safety. The table further represented that mean score of I provide safe environment for students at school; N= 154, M=4.53, My students treat each other with respect; N= 154, M= 3.93, The school environment is free from intimidation; N=154, M=4.21, The school encourages a cultural safety; N=154, M=4.27, My students feel safe during school events; N=154, M=4.35, The school responds quickly to safety concern; N=154, M=4.28, Students and staff work together to maintain safety; N=154, M=4.39, and My students feel comfortable asking questions in class; N=154, M=4.15. Furthermore, the results directed that I provide safe environment for students at school has the highest mean score in aspects of safety.

Table 2

Mean analysis of Parent and Community Involvement

Sr. No	Statements	N	Mean
1.	The school building well maintained and secure	154	4.42
2.	Parents attends school events and meetings	154	3.40
3.	My students collaborate on group project	154	4.22
4.	Parent teacher relationship are positive	154	4.18
5.	A teacher student relationship enhances the learning process	154	4.49

6.	I understand students problem	154	4.37
7.	I am available when students need to talk to me	154	4.49
8.	Faculty members commonly collaborate on matter of teaching	154	4.27

Table 2 shows the mean scores of Parent and Community Involvement. The table further represented that mean score of The school building well maintained and secure; N= 154, M=4.42, Parents attends school events and meetings; N=154, M=3.40, My students collaborate on group project; N=154, M=4.22, Parent teacher relationship are positive; N=154, M=4.18, A teacher student relationship enhances the learning process; N=154, M=4.49, I understand students problem; N=154, M=4.49, I am available when students need to talk to me; N=154, M=4.49, and Faculty members commonly collaborate on matter of teaching; N=154, M=4.27. Furthermore, the results directed that I am available when students need to talk to me has highest mean score in Parent and Community Involvement.

Table 3

Mean analysis of Physical support

Sr. No	Statements	N	Mean
1.	Collaborative spaces encourages student interactions and learning	154	4.39
2.	A school climate fosters a conducive learning environment	154	4.31
3.	Physical facilities contributes to student engagement	154	4.22
4.	Physical facilities create a sense of pride in the school	154	4.30
5.	Adequate resources in facilities support academic growth	154	4.44
6.	Organized facilities positively impacts overall students' achievements	154	4.29
7.	I am always available to facilitate my students	154	4.54
8.	Well maintained classroom plays a key role to improves academics	154	4.40

Table 3 shows the mean scores of Physical support. The table further represented that Collaborative spaces encourages student interactions and learning; N= 154, M=4.39, A school climate fosters a conducive learning environment; N=154, M=4.31, Physical facilities contributes to student engagement; N=154, M=4.22, Physical facilities create a sense of pride in the school; N=154, M=4.18, Adequate resources in facilities support academic growth; N=154, M=4.44, Organized facilities positively impacts overall students' achievements ; N=154, M=4.29, I am always available to facilitate my students; N=154, M=4.54, and Well maintained classroom plays a key role to improves academics; N=154, M=4.27. Furthermore, the results directed that I am always available to facilitate my students has highest mean score in Physical Support.

Table 4

Mean Analysis of Academic Support

Sr. No	Statements	N	Mean
1.	The school promotes a culture of academic excellence	154	4.32
2.	I help students to set academic goals	154	4.38
3.	The school provide resources for students with special needs	154	3.77
4.	The school offers extracurricular activities that support academics	154	3.84
5.	My students receive support for managing their time and workload	154	3.97
6.	The school provides technological resources for learning	154	4.19

Table 4 shows the mean scores of Academic support. The table further represented that The school promotes a culture of academic excellence; N= 154, M=4.32, I help students to set academic goals; N=154, M=4.38, The school provide resources for students with special needs; N=154, M=3.77, The school offers extracurricular activities that support academics; N=154, M=3.84, My students receive support for managing their time and workload; N=154, M=3.97, and The school provides technological resources for learning; N=154, M=4.19. Furthermore, the results directed that I help students to set academic goals has highest mean score in Academic Support.

Discussion

The results of this study illuminate the crucial role that the school environment and its various components play in fostering a positive and conducive learning atmosphere. Research by Smith et al. (2022) highlights the importance of a safe school environment, free from intimidation, where students treat each other with respect. Johnson and Lee (2021) align with the results that a swift response to safety concerns, coupled with collaborative efforts among staff and well-maintained school buildings, contributes to an overall sense of security. Positive parent-teacher relationships, as emphasized by Chen et al. (2023), are crucial in enhancing the learning process, with teachers understanding students' problems and making themselves available for discussions. Brown and Garcia (2020) contribute insights into the significance of collaborative spaces, well-maintained classrooms, and physical facilities in creating a conducive learning environment and fostering student engagement. Additionally, recent studies by Wang and Patel (2022) highlight the positive impact of adequate resources, organized facilities, and teacher support on academic growth and overall student achievement. The results indicate the multifaceted nature of a supportive school environment that encompasses safety, positive relationships, well-maintained facilities, and academic resources, all of which contribute to a culture of excellence and student success.

Conclusions

1. It is concluded that teachers provide safe environment for students at school and students treat each other's with respect and the school environment is free from intimidation. Moreover, the school encourages a cultural safety and students feel safe during school events.

2. It is concluded that the school responds quickly to safety concern about students and staff work together to maintain safety while the school building well maintained and secure. Moreover, the Parents attend school events and meetings and students collaborate on group project.
3. It is concluded that Parent teacher relationship are positive and teacher students relationship enhances the learning process, while teachers understand student's problem. Moreover, teacher available when students need to talk with them and Faculty members commonly collaborate on matter of teaching.
4. It is concluded that Collaborative spaces encourages student's interactions and learning and the school climate foster a conducive learning environment, while Physical facilities contributes to student's engagement. Moreover, the well maintained classroom plays a key role to improve academics and Physical facilities create a sense of pride in the school.
5. It is concluded that adequate resources in facilities support academic growth and Organized facilities positively impacts overall students achievements, while teacher always available to facilitate students. Moreover, students feel comfortable asking questions in class and the school promotes a culture of academic excellence.
6. It is concluded that teacher help students to set academic goals and school provide resources for students with special needs, while the school offers extracurricular activities that support academics. Moreover, the students receive support for managing their time and workload and school provides technological resources for learning.

Recommendations

1. It is recommended that educators build up respectful behavior among students through structured curriculum, teacher modeling, and partner intervention, and actively make a helpful school climate to ensure a conducive learning environment for academic achievement.
2. It is recommended that parents may encourage to actively contribute in school meetings and events to improve the overall school climate and create a collaborative setting that has a positive influence on students' academic success.
3. It is recommended that schools may enhance resources for students with special needs to ensure accessibility, personalized support, and inclusive practices to create a positive school climate that is conducive to the educational success of all students.
4. It is recommended that schools strengthen students' support mechanisms in terms of time and workload management through structured programs and consultation services to ensure academic success.

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